

Leadership Style For Indonesian Public Health Center: Charismatic, Bureaucratic, Transactional, Transformational, Autocratic Or Democratic?

Fatoni¹, Irawan², Suhroji Adha³, Fairus Sintawati⁴, Octoberry Julyanto⁵, Mukhlisin⁶, Ratih Ayu Wulandari⁷, Agus Purwanto⁸

¹Universitas Faletahan, Indonesia

²Universitas Faletahan, Indonesia

³Universitas Faletahan, Indonesia

⁴Universitas Faletahan, Indonesia

⁵Universitas Faletahan, Indonesia

⁶Universitas Faletahan, Indonesia

⁷Universitas Faletahan, Indonesia

⁸Pelita Harapan University, Indonesia

Email: ⁸aguspurwanto.prof@gmail.com

Abstract: *This article analyzes the impact of the leadership style of the head of the public health center in Central Java, Indonesia. The focus is on six main leadership styles, namely transformational, transactional, autocratic, charismatic, bureaucratic and democratic. This article has provided in-depth insights into leadership styles; democratic, transformational, bureaucratic and autocratic leadership have a positive impact on the performance of public health center staff in Central Java, Indonesia. Respondents in this study were 200 public health center staff. Distribution of the questionnaire by means of snowball sampling. The analysis uses a quantitative approach, with the help of a survey instrument, based on a questionnaire survey. Secondary research has been carried out through a previous review of the literature that is set to achieve the research objectives. The results of this article suggest that charismatic, bureaucratic and transactional leadership styles have a negative relationship with performance. A transformational, autocratic, and democratic leadership style, on the other hand, has a positive relationship with the performance of the head of the public health center in Central Java, Indonesia.*

Keywords: *Transformational, Transactional, Autocratic, Bureaucratic, Charismatic, Democratic, Leadership. head of the public health center*

I. INTRODUCTION

The role of leadership in the public health center in Central Java Indonesia is important in terms of creating a vision, mission, setting and establishing goals, designing strategies, policies, and methods to achieve the vision and public health center in Central Java Indonesia effectively and efficiently by directing and coordinating organizational efforts and activities (Xu & Wang, 2008). According to Purwanto (2020), Asbari (2020), Wijayanti (2020) Quality leadership is important to achieve a common mission and vision to overcome changes that occur in the external environment (Harris, et al., 2007). At this time, the public health center

in Central Java, Indonesia, the organizational performance has not been achieved optimally and still needs improvement. Many public health centers in Central Java, Indonesia, to achieve their stated goals, need a public health center leader who effectively coordinates and motivates their employees (Vigoda-Gadot, 2012). Unfortunately some basic public health centers have not taken into account the leadership style adopted by their superiors.

According to Hyun (2020), Mirayani (2020), leaders are effective for several reasons such as charismatic leaders in terms of inspiring their subordinates or subordinates, transformational leaders can meet the emotional needs of subordinates or they can stimulate subordinates intellectually (Bass & Avolio, 1994). Wang et al (2011) found that transformational leadership and follower level of individual performance were positively connected. Furthermore, this study also shows that transformational leadership and team performance at the organizational level are positively associated. Xu and Wang (2010) state that performance is a function of skills, abilities, knowledge and motivation that are directed towards defined behavior. Research conducted by the authors mentioned above shows that transformational leadership enhances the overall development of followers. The followers of transformational leadership associate with self-defining and satisfying, relationships with individuals or groups. The ideal charisma and behavior of transformational leaders motivates followers to identify with the leader (Jyoti & Bhau, 2015). The personalized relationships developed by transformational leaders develop an environment in which subordinates feel happy and hence, their overall performance is enhanced. Therefore, it can be said that transformational leadership and organizational performance are positively related (Jyoti & Bhau, 2015). Sofi and Devanadhen (2015) state that transformational leadership has a significant impact on organizational performance. Research conducted by Purwanto (2020), Asbari (2020), Wijayanti (2020), Santoso (2020), Hyun (2020) and Mirayani (2020) transformational leadership has a direct positive impact on organizational performance.

Based on this premise, this article has been prepared to explore the relationship between the leadership style of public health center heads and public health center performance. There are several types of leadership styles such as transformational leadership, transactional leadership, autocratic, democratic leadership, participatory leadership styles. The leadership styles chosen for this study are charismatic, transformational, transactional, autocratic, bureaucratic, and democratic. The reason for choosing this leadership style is that it is the one most frequently applied as a leadership style throughout Indonesia. The main objective of this research is to determine the impact of autocratic leadership style, democratic leadership style, transactional leadership style, transformational leadership style, charismatic leadership style and bureaucratic leadership style on the performance of public health center staff.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Leadership Style

Leadership style is seen as a combination of various characteristics, traits and behaviors used by leaders to interact with their subordinates. (Mitonga-Monga & oetzee, 2012). Purwanto (2020), Asbari (2020), Wijayanti (2020) consider leadership as a pattern associated with managerial behavior, designed to integrate organizational or personal interests and effects to achieve certain goals. Asbari (2020), Wijayanti (2020) also postulate that leadership style can be defined as the type of relationship used by such an individual to make people work together for a common goal or goal. Based on modern leadership styles, leadership styles can

be categorized as follows: (1) style transformational leadership, (2) transactional leadership style, (3) culture based leadership, (4) charismatic leadership, and (5) visionary leadership (Harris, et al.,2007).

Transformational Leadership Style

According to Purwanto (2020), Asbari (2020), Wijayanti (2020) a transformational leadership style focuses on developing followers and considering their needs. Leaders who focus the focus of transformational leadership in particular on developing the overall value of the subordinate system, developing their morality, skills and motivation levels. Transformational leadership acts as a strong bridge between followers and leaders, to develop a clear understanding of levels of motivation, values and interests. Hyun (2020), Asbari (2020), Santoso (2020) stated that transformational leadership shows leadership that is superior to performance. Transformational leadership, according to Bass and Avolio (1994), occurs when leaders expand or increase employee interest. Transformational leaders are people whose organizational and human abilities are maximized because employees are always able to achieve tangible and intangible gifts. This leadership style in particular helps in creating the optimal existing environment for performance and also articulates a compelling vision that enhances overall organizational performance (Longe, 2014).

Charismatic Leadership Style

According to Purwanto (2020) and Asbari (2020) Charismatic leadership is considered to be one of the most successful leadership styles, in which charismatic leaders develop and followers are asked to follow and carry out their vision and mission. Charismatic leadership invites innovation and creativity from subordinates and is considered as motivation for subordinates. However the main drawback of this charismatic leadership style is that the followers are completely dependent on the leader and once the leader leaves the organization, they become directionless. Hyun (2020), Mirayani (2020) getting worse charismatic leaders do not train their subordinates to act as their substitutes in the future. This leadership style produces happy Followers, but few future leaders. Thus, it can have a long-term, negative effect on organizational performance (Germano, 2010). Ojukuku et al (2012) also stated similar results through their research. They conducted a quantitative study on twenty subordinate survey questionnaires. According to Wijayanti (2020), Santoso (2020), Hyun (2020) their research findings show that charismatic leadership has a negative impact on the relationship with organizational leadership. It does not motivate and encourage subordinates enough to take on the appearance expected of them (Ojukuku, et al., 2012).

Transactional Leadership Style

A leader is known as a transactional leader if he is always willing to give something back (Uchenwamgbe, 2013). This includes things like promotions, raises, performance reviews, new responsibilities. The main problem with this type of leadership is hope. Therefore, transactional leadership can be defined as an exchange of targets and rewards between management and subordinates (Ojukuku, et al., 2012). A study by Longe (2014) revealed that transactional leadership styles have a positive impact on organizational performance. According to Santoso (2020), Hyun (2020), Mirayani (2020), the transactional leadership style helps create and maintain a context in organizational performance as it provides opportunities for subordinates to express and implement their creative ideas and take part in the decision-making process. This leadership style also prepares future leaders and helps the organization in the long run. Wijayanti (2020), Santoso (2020), Hyun (2020) also stated that a democratic leader is a person who focuses on group discussion and group participation and as a result it positively affects the performance of followers. Therefore, a democratic leadership

style can be used to improve organizational performance and efficiency. Therefore, it can be said that democratic leadership has a positive impact on organizational performance (Elenkov, 2002).

Autocratic Leadership Style

Autocratic leaders want their subordinates to work with them. Usually, autocratic leaders maintain decision-making with them (Obiwuru, et al., 2011). The power of autocratic leaders compels their followers to carry out services and strategies their way. According to Purwanto (2020), Asbari (2020), Wijayanti (2020), Santoso (2020), Hyun (2020) and Mirayani (2020) autocratic leadership is also known as authoritarian leadership style, autocratic leaders are less creative and only promote one communication. side. This greatly affects the motivation and satisfaction level of subordinates. Autocratic leadership styles are known to be effective in the short term. Autocratic leadership limits the workplace of two-way socialization and communication. Autocratic leadership also leads to organizational conflicts that have a negative impact on overall performance (Iqbal, et al., 2015). Bhargavi and Yaseen (2016) suggest that autocratic leadership styles have a positive impact on organizational appearance. This leadership style is more suitable when the project must be completed within the target time provided (Bhargavi & Yaseen, 2016). Igbaekemen and Odivwri (2015) also conducted research on the impact of leadership styles on organizational performance. Hyun (2020), Mirayani (2020) stated that autocratic leaders are the only ones who determine the direction of activity policies, to subordinates and expect subordinates to follow all their decisions. In addition, such leaders do not have great confidence in their subordinates.

Bureaucratic Leadership Style

Bureaucratic leaders influence their subordinates to follow the policies and procedures designed by them. According to Asbari (2020), Wijayanti (2020), leaders are very committed to improving their processes and procedures but not their people. This method is not very effective, it does not lead to the development and motivation of subordinates. These leaders only focus their tasks to be completed in a systematic way (Germano, 2010). Ojukuku et al (2012) also stated that leadership bureaucracy has a negative impact on organizational performance. Based on them, bureaucratic leaders do not encourage their organization's subordinates to work in the expected way which can lead to increased organizational performance (Ojukuku, et al., 2012). Santoso (2020), Hyun (2020), Mirayani (2020) also presented similar results which stated that the bureaucratic leadership style did not significantly impact subordinates as well as organizational performance. This method is only useful when the task has to be done for a longer time after the mentioned procedure (Sougui, et al., 2015).

Democratic Leadership Style

Wijayanti (2019), Asbari (2019) define democratic leadership as leadership in which decision making is decentralized and shared by all subordinates. In a democratic leadership style, the potential for weak execution and poor decision making is very high. However, democratic leadership is also known to motivate employees to do better, such as their views and opinions are valued. Studies by Asbari (2019), Santoso (2019) show that democratic leadership has a positive impact on organizational performance. Purwanto (2019) democratic leadership allows employees to make decisions together by sharing them with groups and managers. In this type of leadership style, praise and criticism are given objectively and a sense of responsibility is also developed among employees (Elenkov, 2002). Anggaripeni (2020),

Mirayani (2020) also analyzed the impact of democratic leadership in organizational performance.

III. METHOD

To answer research questions, there are 3 types of research approaches, namely; qualitative methods, quantitative methods, and a mixed approach (Creswell, 2014). According to Kumar (2005), when the aim of the study is to find relationships between variables, quantitative approaches are usually used. This study uses a quantitative approach as the objective is to determine the relationship between the dependent variable of public health center performance and the variable leadership style as the independent variable. Sampling and data collection on the leadership scale for this research work were adopted from Zhu (2002). The research was carried out on all twenty teachers and caretakers. The data were collected using a survey questionnaire. After all procedures, questionnaires were distributed and respondents had to fill them out. Respondents' responses were measured using a five-point Likert scale in which frequency performance was distributed into 5 levels of “never”, “small”, “occasional”, “often” and “always”.

Analysis of the data to calculate the reliability of the data was measured using the Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient. Cronbach's alpha coefficient values for charismatic leadership, bureaucratic leadership, transformational leadership, transactional leadership, democratic leadership and autocratic leadership were found to be 0.813, 0.780, 0.087, 0.790, 0.753, and 0.650, respectively. The impact of the leadership style on their appearance was measured using the organization's performance scale. The scale compares the performance of banks with those of competitors. The reliability and credibility of the scale were checked using item analysis and it yielded a reliability alpha value of 0.76, which was considered quite reliable.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section discusses the findings from secondary data analysis and discussion. The results in the table show that there is a positive and negative relationship between the selected independent variable leadership style and public health center performance. Transactional leadership styles, charismatic leadership, and bureaucratic leadership were found to have negative relationships

relationship with public health center performance with their respective values ($r = -0.136, -0.562, -0.654; P < 0.001$). This shows that the leadership style does not encourage subordinates to perform better in their performance achievements. Leadership styles such as charismatic and bureaucratic are leadership styles that are good for short or small-term projects but for the long term and for the future they are considered unfavorable and do not lead to the development of subordinates. However, democratic leadership styles, transformational leadership styles and autocratic leadership styles have a positive relationship with public health center performance with their respective values ($r = 0.278, 0.145, 0.024; P < 0.001$). This shows that these three leadership styles encourage subordinates to perform better and according to the level of expectations. This leadership style should be promoted in basic public health center organizations.

Table 1. Pearson Correlation: Relationship between Leadership Style and Public Health Center Performance

Variabble	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6
performance	19.067	1.865	1.000					
Transactional	2.234	1.098	-0.136**	1.000				
Transformational	2.876	0.456	0.145**	0.102*	1.000			
Autocratic	1.987	1.245	0.024**	-0.134	-0.107	1.000		
Democracy	3.876	5.453	0.278**	-1.023	0.102	-0.0871	1.000	
Charismatic	2.987	1.145	-0.562**	0.235	-0.213	-0.034	-0.219	1.000
Bureaucracy	1.789	0.675	-0.654*	0.215*	-0.178	0.216	-0.087	-0.089

Tabel 2. Model summary

Model	R	R square	Ajusted R Square	Standard Error	Durbin watson
1	0.468	0.214	0.168	1.34677	1.012

Tabel 3. ANOVA

Model	Total squares	df	Average square	F	sig
Regretion	28.654	5	4.987	2.467	0.53a
Residual	103.098	46	1.845		
Total	1454.765	58			

Tabel 4. Cooefficient

Model	Unstandardized cooeffisient	Std Error	Standardized coefficients Beta	t	sig
Performance	22.034	2.987		5.435	0.000
Transactional	-0.067	0.342	-0.345	-0.198	0.019
Transformational	0.213	0.312	0.023	0.189	0.040
Autocratic	0.056	0.121	0.040	0.497	0.456
Democracy	0.002	0.054	0.001	0.06	0.019
Charismatic	-0.234	0.154	-0.278	-2.135	0.021
Bureaucracy	-0.431	0.213	-0.257	-2.109	0.025

The results of the calculation show that transformational leadership style, transactional leadership style, democratic leadership style and autocratic leadership style predict organizational performance together ($F(5, 42) = 2.646$; $R^2 = 0.214$; $P < 0.05$). Charismatic leadership ($\beta = -0.234$; $t = -2.135$; $P < 0.05$), transactional leadership ($\beta = -0.067$; $t = -0.198$; $P > 0.05$) and bureaucratic leadership ($\beta = -0.431$; $t = -2.109$; $P < 0.05$) has a negative effect on public health center performance. Transformational leadership style ($\beta = 0.213$; $t = 0.189$; $P > 0.05$), democratic leadership style ($\beta = 0.002$; $t = 0.06$; $P < 0.05$) are independent predictors of public health center performance. The results show that the performance of the public health center is influenced by the leadership style. There are three leadership styles that are found to have a positive relationship with public health center performance, namely democratic leadership styles, transformational leadership styles and autocratic leadership styles. The other three leadership styles, namely democratic, transformational and autocratic, were found to have a positive relationship with public health center performance.

The results prove that the leadership style contributes effectively in determining public health center performance. The findings of this study are in line with previous research studies (Wang, et al., 2010; Obiwuru, et al., 2011) that transformational leadership helps build a shared value system giving subordinates the opportunity to develop their skills and abilities. A democratic leadership style helps improve the creativity and decision-making skills of subordinates. In autocratic leadership style, subordinates have to work or follow orders given by the leader and this benefits the organization according to the survey. Charismatic leadership styles and bureaucratic leadership styles have a negative relationship with public health center performance, this is similar to the results shown by Asbari (2020) showing that transactional leadership styles also have a positive impact on public health center performance.

V. CONCLUSION

The article analyzes the impact of the leadership style of the head of the public health center on public health center performance. The focus is on six types of leadership styles - transformational, transactional, democratic, charismatic, bureaucratic, and autocratic. The leadership style of the head of a transformational, autocratic, and democratic public health center has a positive influence on public health center performance, while transactional leadership styles, charismatic and bureaucratic leadership have a negative impact on public health center performance. The analysis of this article reveals that public health center performance is related to leadership style and has positive and negative impacts on performance. A leadership style to offer opportunities to subordinates, offering a sense of belonging by allowing them to participate in decision making. In this context, it is recommended that the head of the public health center should focus on using the transformative leadership style and the democratic leadership style of the head of the public health center to improve the performance of the public health center. This study has provided in-depth insights into the impact of leadership style on performance. However, this article has some limitations such as using only quantitative methods it significantly reduces the scope and applicability of the research. Therefore, future research should focus on using relevant research methods, along with qualitative methods, to determine the relationship between leadership style and public health center performance.

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